

UNIVERZITET U
KRAJUJEVCU
AGRONOMSKI FAKULTET U
ČAČKU

UNIVERSITY OF
KRAJUJEVAC
FACULTY OF
AGRONOMY
ČAČAK

1st INTERNATIONAL SYMPOSIUM ON BIOTECHNOLOGY

17–18 March 2023

Faculty of Agronomy in Čačak, University of Kragujevac, Serbia

- PROCEEDINGS -

1st INTERNATIONAL SYMPOSIUM ON BIOTECHNOLOGY
XXVIII Savetovanje o biotehnologiji sa međunarodnim učešćem

- PROCEEDINGS -

ORGANIZER AND PUBLISHER

University of Kragujevac, Serbia
Faculty of Agronomy in Čačak

Organizing Committee

Prof. Dr Pavle Mašković, Serbia, CHAIR; Dr Vesna Milovanović, Serbia SECRETARY;
MEMBERS: Dr Gorica Paunović, Serbia; Dr Vladimir Dosković, Serbia; Dr Nenad Pavlović, Serbia; Dr Marko Petković, Serbia; Dr Nemanja Miletić, Serbia; Dr Marija Gavrilović, Serbia; Dr Igor Đurović, Serbia; Dr Milevica Bojović, Serbia; Dušan Marković, BSc, Serbia.

International Programme Committee

Prof. Dr Vladimir Kurćubić, Serbia, CHAIR; Prof. Dr Tomo Milošević, Serbia; Prof. Dr Leka Mandić, Serbia; Prof. Dr Milun Petrović, Serbia; Dr Vesna Đorđević, Serbia; Prof. Dr Aleksandar Paunović, Serbia; Dr Čedomir Radović, Serbia; Prof. Dr Vladeta Stevović, Serbia; Prof. Dr Snežana Tanasković, Serbia; Prof. Dr Tomislav Trišović, Serbia; Prof. Dr Gordana Šekularac, Serbia; Dr Jelena Mašković, Serbia; Prof. Dr Andrej Bončina, Slovenia; Dr Kristina Kljak, Croatia; Prof. Dr Milomirka Madić, Serbia; Prof. Dr Snežana Bošković-Bogosavljević, Serbia; Prof. Dr Drago Milošević, Serbia; Prof. Dr Goran Dugalić, Serbia; Prof. Dr Milena Đurić, Serbia; Dr Ivan Glišić, Serbia; Prof. Dr Zvonko Antunović, Croatia; Prof. Dr Enisa Omanović-Mikličanin, B&H; Prof. Dr Ljiljana Bošković-Rakočević, Serbia; Prof. Dr Radojica Đoković, Serbia; Prof. Dr Biljana Veljković, Serbia; Prof. Dr Mlađan Garić, Serbia; Prof. Dr Sanja Radonjić, Montenegro; Dr Goran Marković, Serbia; Prof. Dr Željko Vaško, B&H; Dr Jelena Mladenović, Serbia; Prof. Dr Branko Čupina, Serbia; Dr Milan Nikolić, Serbia; Prof. Dr Vladan Bogdanović, Serbia; Dr Dragan Vujić, Serbia; Dr Marijana Pešaković, Serbia; Dr Simeon Rakonjac, Serbia; Dr Mirjana Radovanović, Serbia; Dr Dalibor Tomić, Serbia; Vera Vukosavljević, MSc, Serbia; Dr Vesna Đurović, Serbia; Dr Adrijana Filipović, B&H; Prof. Dr Ivana Janeska-Stamenkoska, North Macedonia; Dragan Đurović, MSc, Serbia; Radmila Ilić, BSc, Serbia; Miloš Marjanović, MSc, Serbia; Jelena Pantović, BSc, Serbia.

Technical editors

Prof. Dr Pavle Mašković; Dr Vesna Milovanović; Dušan Marković, BSc

Print-run: 100

Printed by

Copy Xerox, Cara Dušana 11, 32000 Čačak

ISBN 978-86-87611-88-7

Year of publication: 2023

© Faculty of Agronomy in Čačak 2023

PROMOTING SMART AGRICULTURAL PRACTICES IN MAIZE PRODUCTION IN BIH - H2020 SMARTWATER PROJECT

Mihajlo Marković¹, Nataša Čereković¹, Đurađ Hajder¹, Milan Šipka¹, Nery Zapata², Teresa A. Paço³, Erminio E. Riezzo⁴, Sabrija Čadro⁵, Mladen Todorović⁶

Abstract: Agricultural practices in Bosnia and Herzegovina demand different improvements, including smart management of land and water resources. A new H2020 project started in 2021 in this regard. The objective of this publication is to spread knowledge about SMARTWATER project by describing different achievements in two years of implementation (2021-2022), to invite target groups to participate in the action and to promote smart agricultural practices. Presented results indicate that the implementation is at a satisfactory level. Project consortium will continue with efforts, including twinning, networking, research, dissemination and increasing competency and fund rising skills.

Keywords: twinning, research, exchange, irrigation, smart technologies

Introduction and literature review

Smart management of land and water resources in Bosnia and Herzegovina (BiH), as a country with a good irrigation potential but rainfed agriculture practices, is very important (World Bank, 2012; FAO, 2017). In line with these a new H2020 project SMARTWATER² started with its implementation on the 1st of January 2021. The main research themes are in line with the needs of BiH agriculture and relevant research, and include: 1) cloud-based smart technologies (Romero et al., 2012; Todorovic et al., 2016), 2) new generation of satellite remote sensing data (Paço et al., 2014; Mateos et al., 2013), 3) water-energy-food nexus (Zapata et al., 2017) and 4) climate change impact to agriculture (Stričević et al., 2014; Todorovic et al., 2018). The effect of irrigation

¹ University of Banja Luka, Faculty of Agriculture, Bulevar v. Petra Bojovića 1A, Banja Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina (mihajlo.markovic@agro.unibl.org); ² Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Cientificas, Calle Serrano 117, Madrid, Spain; ³ Universidade de Lisboa, Instituto Superior de Agronomia, Tapada da Ajuda 1349-017, Lisbon, Portugal; ⁴ SYSMAN PROGETTI & SERVIZI SRL, Via G. Lorenzoni 19, Roma, Italy; ⁵ University of Sarajevo, Faculty of Agriculture and Food Science, Zmaja od Bosne 8, Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina; ⁶ Centro Internazionale di Altistudi Agronomici Mediterranei, Via Ceglie 9, Valenzano, Italy.

²<http://www.smartwater-project.eu/>

and fertilization treatments was studied in maize (Živanović et al., 2015; Kresović et al., 2016; Stričević et al., 2017; Dodig et al., 2021).

The main objective of SMARTWATER is to reinforce new networking, research and S&T cooperation capacities of the University of Banja Luka (UNI-BL), the University of Sarajevo (UNSA) and other connected national institutions, in the field of sustainable agricultural water management and to increase their competency and fund raising skills for a successful participation in the European Union Research Programs.³The project duration is 36 months. SMARTWATER consortium consists of six partners⁴: UNI-BL, CIHEAM-IAMB, CSIC, ISA, SYS and UNSA and implementation is planned through five Work Packages (WPs).

The objective of this paper is to spread knowledge about SMARTWATER project by describing achievements in two years of implementation (2021-2022), to invite all project target groups to participate in the action and to promote smart and sustainable practices in agriculture in Bosnia and Hercegovina.

Opening new horizons: the project implementation started in 2021

period January-June 2021

The H2020 SMARTWATER project started with its implementation on the 1st of January 2021. The first activity was kick-off meeting, held in a hybrid form (27.1.). The event gathered 36 participants and great outcomes were achieved.

The dissemination was done in order to spread knowledge about project and to gather and involve target groups. We established SMARTWATER project logo and official website, as well as social media profiles on *Facebook*, *Twitter*, *LinkedIn* and *YouTube*, published posts and news. The joint experimental studies (WP3) were prepared. We published the info for master course in Bari (Italy) at CIHEAM-IAMB (WP2).

The UNI-BL team participated in the REA Cluster Event⁵(20.5.) and in symposium AgroReS 2021⁶ (27-28.5.). The 1st stakeholders' meeting was

³European Commission (2020). Grant Agreement, project number 952396, SMARTWATER.

⁴UNI-BL (UNIVERZITET U BANJOJ LUCI), CIHEAM-IAMB (CENTRO INTERNAZIONALE DI ALTISTUDI AGRONOMICI MEDITERRANEI), CSIC (AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS), ISA (INSTITUTO SUPERIOR DE AGRONOMIA), SYS (SYSMAN PROGETTI & SERVIZI SRL), UNSA (UNIVERZITET U SARAJEVU).

⁵<https://faster-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/Final-report-Cluster-meeting-Agri-Nat-Res.pdf>

⁶<https://agrores.net/en/>

organized by UNSA (7.6.) and more than 30 participants joined. We also prepared and submitted to the European Commission (EC) project reports (deliverables) in WP1 and WP5.

period July-December 2021

The main project activity in this period was the 1st summer school. It was organized by UNI-BL in BiH in Trebinje (30.8. – 3.9.) and 40 participants joined. The topic was "*Integrated approach for agricultural water management*".

Project financial and administrative issues were discussed. We worked on the equipment procurement. Also, cultivations and plant and soil samplings in maize were done. SMARTWATER project was presented in an interview to INTRASOFT International⁷. We participated in the ERA *Info Day*⁸ event(9.7.). We joined two conferences, "*Soils for future under global challenges*" organized in Serbia (21-24.9.) and "*Agrosym 2021*" organized in BiH (7-10.10.)⁹.

As one of the main activities, ISA organized the first advanced training course in Portugal in Lisbon(27.9. – 1.10)and 32 people joined. The topic was "*Advanced remote sensing technologies and tools for crop water requirements estimates and irrigation scheduling*".

Master students started their course (1.10.). CATCHaCORN¹⁰ students' competition was organized (24.10.). Dissemination activities were pronounced and SMARTWATER was further promoted. The 1st year of experiments was finished. The remaining project reports in 2021 were sent to EC.

Staying in lane: the project implementation continued in 2022

period January - June 2022

The second project year has started with a lot of experience behind us. We begin to prepare data for the 1st periodic report and to implement forthcoming activities. Dissemination activities continued. The 2nd year of experiments was prepared. We joined the "*World Water Day*¹¹" in Patras in Greece (22.5.) and the "

⁷<https://www.netcompany-intrasoft.com/>

⁸https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/events/horizon-europe-info-days/era-and-widening/july-2021_en

⁹<https://congress.sdpz.rs/> and <http://agrosym.ues.rs.ba/>

¹⁰<http://www.smartwater-project.eu/the-first-competition-in-maize-harvesting-catchacorn-event/>

¹¹<http://www.smartwater-project.eu/world-water-day-22-march-2022-patras-greece/>

5th International Scientific Conference on Water¹² in Szarvas in Hungary (22-24.3.).

We continued to cooperate with similar H2020 projects. We presented the project at “AgroReS 2022¹³” (26-28.5., Trebinje, BiH). ISA team joined the “ENCONTRO CIÊNCIA¹⁴” in Lisbon (Portugal) from 16th to 18th of May 2022.

UNSA team organized the second stakeholders’ meeting (20.6.). The topic was “Promotion of sustainable agricultural water managements practices in Bosnia and Herzegovina” and 83 participants joined. ISA participated in the “National Fair of Agriculture” in Portugal (4-12.6.). Two students from BiH were awarded master’s degree at CIHEAM-IAMB. We submitted reports in WP 1, WP 4 and WP 5.

period July- December 2022

The main project activity in this period was the second summer school. It was organized by UNSA in Sarajevo in BiH (18-22.7) with 46 participants. The topic was “Smart technologies and best practices (technical and practical) for sustainable and environmentally efficient water management in agriculture”. SMARTWATER was presented at the “International Symposium on Managing Land and Water for Climate-Smart Agriculture¹⁵” held in Vienna in Austria (25-29.7.). Project reports in WP 2 and WP 5 were submitted. UNSA team organized the first workshop on funding opportunities and proposal drafting in Sarajevo in BiH (11-13.10.). We presented SMARTWATER at three conferences, the first one was held in Velke Bilovice¹⁶ in Czech Republic (6-7.10.), the second one in Ohrid¹⁷ in North Macedonia (12-14.10.) and the third one in Beja¹⁸ in Portugal (18-20.10.).

As one of the main activities, CSIC organized the second advanced training course in Zaragoza in Spain (26-30.9.) and more than 20 people joined. The topic was “Use of innovative technologies and tools for collective and on-demand pressurized irrigation systems”.

¹²<http://www.smartwater-project.eu/5th-international-scientific-conference-on-water/>

¹³<https://agrores.net/en/>

¹⁴<https://www.encontrociencia.pt/2022/>

¹⁵<http://www.smartwater-project.eu/smartwater-project-at-the-international-symposium-on-managing-land-and-water-for-climate-smart-agriculture/>

¹⁶<http://www.smartwater-project.eu/smartwater-project-at-the-international-conference-on-urban-water-2022/>

¹⁷ <https://isaf2022.isaf.edu.mk/>

¹⁸<http://www.smartwater-project.eu/smartwater-project-at-ix-national-congress-on-irrigation-and-drainage-in-beja-portugal/>

The second PSG_SEAB meeting was held by UNI-BL in Banja Luka and Teslić (BiH), from 13th to 16th of December 2022. This was great opportunity to gather all PSG and SEAB members, to have the overview of activities and achievements in two years of project implementation and to plan future activities.

At the end of 2022 we summarized our efforts, sent all the necessary project reports and established the framework for the activities in 2023. The effort of SMARTWATER project consortium in 2021 and 2022, when it comes to the pre-defined activities, is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. The overview of activities within SMARTWATER project in 2021 and 2022

<i>no.</i>	<i>Activity type</i>	<i>Accomplished</i>	<i>Project report reference</i>
1	advanced training courses	2/3	D2.4 / D5.9
2	summer schools	2/3	D2.3 / D5.8
3	joint research activities	2/3	D3.1 / D3.2 / D3.3
4	meetings – roundtable debates	2/3	D4.3
5	post-graduate MSc programs	3/3 (1 st year)	D2.8 / D2.9 / D2.10
6	mutual staff exchanges	3/13	D3.1 / D3.2 / D3.3
7	hands-on workshops	1/3	D2.5
8	international conferences	13/3	-
9	smart water management tools	2/2	-

Slowing down: future plans and activities in 2023

In 2023, SMARTWATER project life will hopefully continue. The activities to be organized include remaining advanced courses, summer schools and exchanges, the last year of MSc and experimental studies, and the last year of stakeholders' meetings, hands-on workshops and participation to conferences.

Joint experimental studies – basic considerations

Within WP 3, the joint research includes experiments in 3 years and at two locations in BiH (Aleksandrovac and Butmir). The target plant species is maize (*Zea mays* L.), hybrid BL 43 (FAO 400 group). The RCB design include two factors, irrigation (3 irrigation levels) and fertilization (2 nitrogen levels). The aim of these experiments is to find the best combination of irrigation and fertilization treatments in maize production in agro-ecological conditions of Banja Luka and Sarajevo (BiH) and to promote smart agricultural practices in land and water management in agriculture in BiH.

Conclusion

In two years of SMARTWATER project implementation a lot of twinning activities were performed. We organized summer schools and advanced courses, participated in more than 15 conferences in BiH and abroad, joined 6 EC workshops, and had 2 stakeholders' meetings. Along with these, we have worked on project reports, dissemination, staff exchange and publications within the main research themes. Our mutual efforts contributed the increase of networking and research between UNI-BL, UNSA and connected institutions and the increase of our competency and fund rising skills for new proposals toward the EC, which are the main project objectives. The presence of a lot of activities in 2023 should not stop project consortium in putting more effort to achieve goals and to work on project legacy.

Acknowledgement

The research presented in this article is part of the SMARTWATER project (Grant Agreement No 952396) financially supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

References

- DodigD., Božinović S., Nikolić A., Zorić M., Vančetović J., Ignjatović-MicićD., Delić N., Weigelt K., Altmann T., Junker A. (2021). Dynamics of maize vegetative growth and drought adaptability using image-based phenotyping under controlled conditions. *Frontiers in Plant Science*. 12(2021).
- FAO (2017). *The state of food security and nutrition in Europe and Central Asia*. Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations, Budapest, 80 pp.
- Kresović B., TapanarovaA., Tomić Z., Životić Lj., Vujović D., Sredojević Z., GajićB. (2016). Grain yield and water use efficiency of maize as influenced by different irrigation regimes through sprinkler irrigation under temperate climate. *Agricultural Water Management*. 169(2016): 34-43.
- Mateos L., González-Dugo M.P., Testi L., Villalobos F.J. (2013). Monitoring evapotranspiration of irrigated crops using crop coefficients derived from time series of satellite images. I. Method validation. *Agricultural Water Management*, 125: 81-91.

- Paço T.A., Pôças I., Cunha M., Silvestre J.C., Santos F.L., Paredes P., Pereira L.S. (2014). Evapotranspiration and crop coefficients for a super intensive olive orchard. An application of SIMDualKc and METRIC models using ground and satellite observations. *Journal of Hydrology*, 519:2067-2080.
- Romero R., Muriel J.L., Garcia I., Munoz de la Pena D. (2012). Research on automatic irrigation control: state of the art and recent results. *Agricultural Water Management*, 114: 9-66.
- Stričević R.J., Djurović N.Lj., Vuković A.J., Vujadinović M.P., Ćosić M.D., Pejić B.S. (2014). Application of Aquacrop model for yield and irrigation requirement estimation of sugar beet under climate change conditions in Serbia. *Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 59(3): 301-317.
- Stričević R., Stojakovic N., Vujadinovic-Mandic M., Todorovic M. (2017). Impact of climate change on yield, irrigation requirements and water productivity of maize cultivated under the moderate continental climate of Bosnia and Herzegovina. *The Journal of Agricultural Science*, 156(5): 618-627.
- Todorovic M., Mehmeti A., Cantore V. (2018). Impact of different water and nitrogen inputs on the eco-efficiency of durum wheat cultivation in Mediterranean Environments. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 183: 1276-1288.
- Todorovic M., Riezzo E.E., Buono V., Zippitelli M., Galiano A., Cantore V. (2016). Hydro-Tech: an automated smart-tech Decision Support Tool for eco-efficient irrigation management, *International Agricultural Engineering Journal*, 25(2): 44-56.
- World Bank (2012). Project appraisal document on a proposed credit to Bosnia and Herzegovina for an irrigation development project. Report N° 65984-BA, Washington DC, 74 pp.
- Zapata N., El Malki E.H., Latorre B., Gallinat J., Citoler F.J., Castillo R., Playán, E. (2017). A simulation tool for advanced design and management of collective sprinkler irrigated areas: a study case. *Irrigation Science*, 35(4): 327-345.
- Živanović Lj., Kovačević V., Lukić V. (2015). Economic cost – effectiveness of different nitrogen application in the production of corn on chernozems soil. *Economics of Agriculture*, 62(2): 421-436.

CIP - Каталогизacija у публикацији
Народна библиотека Србије, Београд

63(082)
606:63(082)

INTERNATIONAL Symposium on Biotechnology (1 ; 2023 ; Čačak)

Proceedings / 1st International Symposium on Biotechnology, 17–18 March 2023 ; [organizer] University of Kragujevac, Faculty of Agronomy [in] Čačak. - Kragujevac : University, Faculty of Agronomy in Čačak, 2023 (Čačak : Copy Xerox). - 555 str. : ilustr. ; 24 cm

Na vrhu nasl. str.: Univerzitet u Kragujevcu, Agronomski fakultet u Čačku. - "XXVIII Savetovanje o biotehnologiji sa međunarodnim učešćem" --> kolofon. - Tiraž 100. - Bibliografija uz svaki rad.

ISBN 978-86-87611-88-7

a) Пољопривреда -- Зборници б) Биотехнологија -- Зборници

COBISS.SR-ID 110983945

DOI: [10.46793/NasKg2252](https://doi.org/10.46793/NasKg2252)